

Big Data in SHELA: Investigating star-formation regulation at high redshift with progenitors of massive quiescent galaxies

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Motivation:

Recent ground- and space-based studies have found that the characteristic luminosity of the rest-frame ultraviolet (UV) luminosity function is nearly constant at $z > 4$ (Finkelstein+15).

As the UV luminosity function traces recent star formation, this implies that galaxies maintain comparable levels of star formation as redshift increases. While the efficiency of galaxies to convert gas into stars could increase as redshift increases, the lack of metals at early times should reduce the amount cold gas available for star formation. An alternative possibility is that feedback from accreting super-massive black holes (SMBHs) has a lower impact on suppressing star formation at earlier times.

What we did:

We present the most-detailed probe yet into the impact of accreting SMBH or active galactic nuclei (AGN) feedback on star formation by measuring the shape of the bright end of the galaxy UV luminosity function at $z \sim 4$.

What we found:

We found an excess of galaxies at the bright-end of the galaxy luminosity function implying some factor, perhaps AGN feedback, is weaker at suppressing star formation at high redshift.

SHELA is the *Spitzer* HETDEX Exploratory Large Area, a 24 deg² field within SDSS Stripe-82 covered by eight deep visible-to-IR photometric surveys and the forth-coming blind visible spectra of HETDEX.

SHELA 3.6 micron map

The multi-wavelength nature of the SHELA survey is uniquely suited to study rare massive galaxies and clusters during cosmic high-noon ($z \sim 2$) and cosmic brunch ($z > 3$) with minimal low- z contaminants.

The imaging in the SHELA field includes:

- Mid-IR imaging from *Spitzer* IRAC With 3σ AB mag limits of $m_{3.6\mu m} = 22.8$ and $m_{4.5\mu m} = 22.3$.
- Optical imaging with the Dark Energy Camera (DECam; PI Papovich) to depths of $m_{AB} \sim 25.5$ for ugriz filters.
- NOAO/NEWFIRM K-band ($2.1 \mu m$) imaging to $K_{AB} = 23$ from the NEWFIRM-HETDEX survey (PI Finkelstein).

We selected our $z \sim 4$ sample using the redshift probability distribution functions (PDFs) from the EAZY photometric redshift fitting code (Brammer+08).

Selection criteria are as follows:

1. r' and i' bands must have $S/N > 3.5$, respectively.
2. PDF integral at $z > 3.5$ must be greater than 0.5.
3. Integral of PDF for $3.5 < z < 4.5$ must be greater than any other $\Delta z = 1$ bin.
4. Positive random forest algorithm classification.

Our final sample had 5,736 objects.

We used the supervised machine-learning algorithm, random forest, to remove bright low- z older-star-dominated galaxies and evolved stars like the one shown here.

We trained the random forest algorithm by classifying by eye the r -band-brightest 200 objects that passed the PDF selection process. The algorithm uses 17 features, 1000 decision-tree estimators, and balanced classes. With just two classes (obviously high- z sources and obviously low- z sources) we set the the max depth to two. The $i' - ch2$ color was found to be the most important feature when training the random forest.

We found an excess of bright galaxies over Schechter and fit a double power-law to bins where number counts exceed the AGN luminosity function and bins of galaxy luminosity functions from deep surveys.

We avoided the challenge of removing AGN contaminants by keeping them in our sample. Our combined luminosity function is consistent with the SDSS AGN luminosity function at brighter magnitudes and space-based galaxy luminosity functions at fainter magnitudes.

